

International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews

Journal homepage: www.ijrpr.com ISSN 2582-7421

Personalized Content Delivery in Content-Centric Online Learning

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ABSTRACT

Personalization of online learning has become essential in the improvement of student satisfaction, motivation, and learning. With rapid growth of web-based systems like NPTEL students are introduced to thousands of courses, and this normally ends up in information overload. The proposed project is in the form of a content-based course recommender system that offers learners personalized content in an online learning platform that revolves around content. TF-IDF vectorization and cosine similarity are utilized in the system to provide recommendations through handling textual data in course names, descriptions, and instructors. Streamlit offers a user interface for the learner to engage through modules such as search, personal interests, departments wise grouping, and visualizations of datasets. Performance was measured based on metrics such as Precision@K, Recall@K, MAP, and NDCG, where TF-IDF was consistently superior to the baseline Count Vectorizer. This study indicates that content-based filtering has the potential to greatly enhance online learning by offering tailored recommendations synchronized with learning needs.

Keywords: Personalization, E-learning, Content-Based Filtering, TF-IDF, Cosine Similarity, Course Recommendation

1. Introduction

The advent of web-based learning sites such as NPTEL, Coursera, and edX has provided students with access to thousands of courses in various fields. Though this offers students more power, it also causes information overload, where students lack the ability to find courses that suit their individual objectives. Classic keyword searches rarely provide personalized results. To resolve this problem, recommender systems have become a central solution. They serve to filter and rank information according to user requirement. Of the various types collaborative filtering [3], content-based filtering [2], and hybrid recommenders [4] content-based filtering has been chosen in this project, which relies on course metadata and text descriptions for recommendation. By developing a customized recommender system for NPTEL courses, utilizing TF-IDF and cosine similarity [1], and offering an interactive interface to showcase the system's capabilities, this work makes a contribution.

2. Literature Review

Recommender systems that are content-based examine item descriptions and contrast them with user preferences. One of the best methods for text-based recommendations is still TF-IDF [1] (Salton et al., 1988). A common method for determining how close two document vectors are to one another is cosine similarity.

Despite using user interactions, collaborative filtering (Schafer et al., 2007) [3] has a cold-start issue. Both strategies are combined in hybrid systems [4](Burke, 2002) for improved performance. Although they are computationally demanding, deep learning techniques like BERT-based recommenders [5] (Zhou et al., 2021) have recently been introduced.

3. Methodology

There are multiple steps in the methodology:

- 1.Dataset Preparation: Course title, description, instructor, timeline, URL, and other attributes were gathered from the NPTEL dataset. The year and length of the course were extracted, and missing values were handled.
- 2.Text Preprocessing & Department Assignment: Using keyword rules, departments (such as CSE, Electrical, Mechanical, Civil, etc.) were automatically assigned after text fields were cleaned and combined.
- 3.Feature Extraction: Text was converted into numerical vectors using Count Vectorizer and TF-IDF [1].
- 4.Similarity Computation: To determine how related course vectors are to one another, cosine similarity [1] was calculated.

4. System Architecture

The proposed system architecture Dataset → Preprocessing → Feature Extraction → Similarity Computation → Recommendation Engine → Visualization & Evaluation → User Interface.

Figure 1: System Architecture Diagram of the Recommender System

This modular design ensures scalability and clear flow from raw data to final user recommendations.

5. Implementation

The system was implemented using **Streamlit** for the frontend and **scikit-learn** for machine learning tasks. The following modules were developed:

- **Search & Recommend Module:** Users can select a course and view top-N similar courses.

title	instructor	timeline	url	year	duration_months	department	similarity
A Brief Course on Superconductivity	Prof. Saurabh Basu	{'course_duration': {'start_date': 'jan 2020', 'end_date': 'feb 2020'}, 'enrollment': {'start_date': '18-nov-2019', 'end_date': '03-feb-2020'}, 'exam_registration': {'start_date': '16-dec-2019', 'end_date': '21-feb-2020'}, 'exam_date': '29-mar-2020'}	Click Here	2020	1	Computer Science	1
A brief course on Superconductivity	Prof. Saurabh Basu	{'course_duration': {'start_date': 'jan 2021', 'end_date': 'feb 2021'}, 'enrollment': {'start_date': '18-nov-2020', 'end_date': '25-jan-2021'}, 'exam_registration': {'start_date': '15-jan-2021', 'end_date': '12-feb-2021'}, 'exam_date': '21-mar-2021'}	Click Here	2021	1	Computer Science	1

Figure 2: Screenshot of course search and recommendation results

- **Preference Personalized Module:** Users input keywords (e.g., “Python, AI”), and the system generates recommendation.

Figure 3: Screenshot of personalized recommendations from preference

- **Department-wise Module:** Courses are grouped by domain, and recommendations are provided department-wise.

Figure 4: Screenshot of department-wise recommendations

- **Visualization Module:** Includes instructor frequency, course trends per year, department distribution

Figure 5: Screenshot of visualization

6. Results and Evaluation

The system was evaluated with sample queries (“Python,” “AI,” “Data Science”) using metrics such as:

- **Precision@K:** Ratio of relevant courses retrieved among top-K.
- **Recall@K:** Ratio of relevant courses retrieved among all relevant courses.
- **MAP (Mean Average Precision):** Measures ranking quality.
- **NDCG:** Considers the position of relevant results.

Results showed that **TF-IDF consistently outperformed Count Vectorizer** across all metrics.

Figure 6: Screenshot of evaluation metrics table (Precision, Recall, NDCG

Figure 7: Screenshot of bar chart comparing TF-IDF vs Count Vectorizer results

7. Conclusion

This project developed a **content-based course recommender system** for online learning platforms like NPTEL. Using TF-IDF and cosine similarity, it successfully delivered personalized course recommendations. With additional modules for search, likes, visualization, and evaluation, the system demonstrates practical value. Evaluation proved that TF-IDF outperforms Count Vectorizer, showing its effectiveness for text-based recommendations.

The study confirms that **personalized content delivery in content-centric online learning** enhances learner experience by reducing information overload and guiding students toward relevant resources.

8. Future Enhancements

This system can be extended through the integration of advanced deep learning models such as BERT and Transformers [5], which are capable of capturing deeper semantic relationships within course descriptions, learner queries, and instructor profiles. Incorporating such models would significantly improve the contextual understanding of content and result in more accurate recommendations. Another enhancement lies in the development of hybrid recommenders [4] by combining content-based filtering with collaborative filtering techniques, thereby addressing the limitations of each individual approach and improving both accuracy and diversity of the suggestions. Additionally, real-time deployment into Learning

Management Systems (LMS) such as Moodle or SWAYAM would provide seamless accessibility to learners, enabling them to receive personalized recommendations directly within their learning environments. Finally, instead of limiting suggestions to individual courses, the system can be further refined to generate personalized learning paths, where a structured sequence of courses is recommended based on learners' prior knowledge, interests, and long-term academic or professional objectives.

9. References

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